

DEGRADATION OF NICALON FIBRES IN MAGNESIUM-BASED COMPOSITE.

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ABSTRACT.

Composites based upon magnesium reinforced with Nicalon (a silicon carbide based fibre) have been manufactured by liquid metal infiltration, using temperatures of 700°C. and 900°C., and their microstructures examined using optical and electron microscopy combined with electron-probe microanalysis. Fibres within the composite were found to have an annular ring appearance indicating a reaction had occurred in the outer regions. Analytical scanning electron microscopy demonstrated that magnesium had diffused from the matrix into the surface regions of the fibre to form an oxide of magnesium. The reaction was accompanied by the displacement of silicon from the fibre which combined with magnesium in the matrix to form magnesium silicide, Mg_2Si . At the higher manufacturing temperature, silicon carbide particles and spinel oxide, $MgAl_2O_4$, were also formed in the matrix.

1. INTRODUCTION

The demand for strong materials with high specific properties has generated interest in metal matrix composites (MMC) based upon magnesium because of the low density of the metal, $1.74gcm^{-3}$ as compared with $2.7gcm^{-3}$ for aluminium. However, magnesium tends to be highly reactive in certain environments and severe problems may arise concerning its compatibility with the reinforcement. In particular, chemical reactions may be induced at the temperature of manufacture of the MMC or as a result of subsequent heat treatment. Such changes will undoubtedly affect the structure of the interface between reinforcement and matrix and, in turn, the integrity of the mechanical bond, usually adversely. Here, as part of an ongoing programme aimed at the development of magnesium alloys reinforced with continuous fibres, data are reported on the behaviour of Nicalon (a SiC-based fibre) in composites which have been manufactured by liquid metal infiltration at two different temperatures.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Two composites were prepared using a liquid metal infiltration (LMI) process. They both contained Nicalon, a continuous $\sim 13\mu m$ diameter fibre based upon silicon carbide which is made by pyrolysis of an organo-metallic filament (1).

(i). This composite material had a matrix based upon commercial purity magnesium. The fibres were filament wound and placed lengthwise in a die heated to $\sim 400^\circ C$. prior to infiltration. The liquid metal was contained in a crucible maintained at $\sim 700^\circ C$. and allowed to permeate the preform at low pressure, $\sim 7MPa$ (2), such that the liquid front was parallel to the length of the fibres. The final composite was in the form of 2mm thick sheet some 100mm square with a nominal fibre volume fraction of 40%.

(ii). The matrix metal used for this composite was AZ31 (3wt.% aluminium, 1wt.% zinc with 0.5wt.% of manganese added for corrosion resistance), a general purpose magnesium alloy with suitable casting characteristics for the LMI process. The fibres were stacked lengthwise in a cylindrical steel tube and placed in the heated die. The metal was held at ~900°C. in the crucible before it was allowed to infiltrate at low pressure the fibre preform, the liquid front moving perpendicularly to the length of the fibres. The composite was produced as rod, ~100mm long and 10mm diameter, with the fibres aligned along the axis to give a nominal volume fraction of 10%.

Samples for optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were prepared by metallographic polishing on successively finer diamond slurries. Difficulties arose due to relief polishing around the fibres and the tendency of water-based polishing suspensions to etch matrix second phases, but eventually satisfactory surfaces were produced, as may be seen in Fig. 1. Thin electron-transparent specimens for TEM were prepared by a combination of dimpling and ion beam milling techniques; in the case of the high-temperature (900°C.) sample, fibres often became detached from the matrix before the necessary thinning had occurred.

Examination by SEM was carried out using a JEOL 35C instrument to which was attached an energy-dispersive x-ray spectrometer (EDS) for compositional analysis, and by TEM in a JEOL 2000FX also fitted with EDS. Some phase analyses were performed using a JEOL 8600 superprobe equipped with a wavelength-dispersive system (WDS).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Composite manufactured at 700°C.

The microstructure of this composite, Fig. 1a, showed that it had been well infiltrated with metal. The amount of porosity present was very little and this tended to occur mainly where fibres were closely spaced. SEM examination using backscattered electrons, Fig. 1b, indicated that a reaction zone, no more than ~200nm thick had formed at fibre surfaces. It was, however, difficult to obtain quantitative analysis data on the reaction zone because of its narrow width compared with the volume of material (a cubic μm or so) being excited by the electron probe. Analysis of the unreacted central region of a fibre using WDS showed that it contained ~55% silicon, ~32% carbon and ~12% oxygen (all values in wt.%), in close agreement with previous results on as-received Nicalon fibre (3). A second phase, up to 40 μm in length and ~1 μm across, is visible in the matrix which EDS analysis revealed contained magnesium and silicon in the ratio of 2:1, thus identifying it as the intermetallic Mg_2Si .

Fig. 2a is a transmission electron micrograph taken from the fibre/matrix interface which shows the formation in fibre surface regions of a reaction zone ~100nm thick. A fairly high density of dislocations is present in the matrix adjacent to the fibre. A selected area diffraction (SAD) pattern from the fibre core, Fig. 2b, contains diffuse rings which are consistent with the presence of finely-crystalline $\beta\text{-SiC}$ (fcc structure with $a = 4.36\text{\AA}$), and appreciable background scattering as may arise from the presence of amorphous material. The SAD pattern from the reacted zone, Fig. 2c, is significantly different, with the appearance of well-defined spotty rings and a reduction in the amount of amorphous scattering; the diffuse rings which relate to the finely-crystalline SiC structure are still visible. Analysis of the spotty rings indicated the presence of an fcc structure with a lattice parameter of 4.21 \AA , in accord with crystalline magnesium oxide. Analysis using EDS, Fig. 3a, confirmed the presence of silicon, carbon and oxygen in the fibre core and also the marked changes in composition occurring in outermost regions, as exemplified by high

magnesium level coupled with reduced amount of silicon, Fig. 3b. Large particles were frequently located in the matrix, Fig. 4a, the corresponding SAD pattern, Fig. 4b, and the relevant EDS data, Fig. 4c, identifying the phase as Mg_2Si , an fcc structure with $a = 6.35\text{\AA}$; the diffraction data are indexed accordingly in Fig. 4d, where the electron beam direction is identified as $[0\bar{3}1]$.

3.2. Composite manufactured at 900°C.

Seen at low optical magnification, it was apparent that some displacement of the Nicalon fibres towards the outer region of the composite had been produced by the pressure of the liquid metal front during infiltration. The general alignment of the fibres remained, however, essentially unidirectional. At higher magnification (Fig. 5), each fibre is seen to have an 'annular' ring appearance, characteristic of a reaction having occurred in surface regions. An SEM picture obtained using backscattered electrons, Fig. 6, clearly revealed the extent of reaction zone in the fibres, the lighter appearance of the outer region indicating that its average atomic weight is higher than that of the fibre core. Some small ($\sim 1\mu\text{m}$) pores were present in the matrix and there was evidence of decohesion having occurred between fibre and matrix, but these effects are believed to be a consequence of the fibre/matrix interdiffusion processes which accompanied the interface reaction occurring during manufacture. The fibre/matrix interaction appeared to be much more extensive in this composite, with the formation of a substantially thicker reaction zone compared with that produced at 700°C. The degree of reaction differed from fibre to fibre, and sometimes a planar interface defined the reacted and unreacted zones in such a way that it appeared to bisect the fibre. The dimensions of the reacted zone meant that sensible quantitative analysis could be achieved and WDS analysis was able to show that it contained up to ~ 54 wt.% magnesium and $\sim 25\%$ silicon, with the carbon level appreciably lower ($\sim 15\%$) and the oxygen slightly higher than in the core. The penetration of magnesium into the fibre was accompanied by rejection of silicon into the metal matrix. Several different types of intermetallic phase were found. Firstly, large angular particles were present, often $50\mu\text{m}$ or more in size, and these were found, using EDS, to be Mg_2Si . Particles of up to $100\mu\text{m}$ in length and up to $2\mu\text{m}$ across were also identified as Mg_2Si phase. In matrix regions adjacent to the most heavily-reacted fibres, fairly large particles (labelled A in Fig.7) were found which contained silicon and carbon in proportions consistent with SiC. Close to the fibres, especially the most heavily-reacted, were acicular-shaped particles up to $15\mu\text{m}$ long and $\sim 1\mu\text{m}$ thick (B) consisting of magnesium, aluminium and oxygen, the largest having a composition close to that of spinel, $Mg\text{Al}_2\text{O}_4$. Some variation in the apparent composition of the needle-like particles was noted but this was believed to be a size effect relating to some electron excitation of the surrounding matrix.

4. DISCUSSION

Appreciable reaction occurred between Nicalon fibre and magnesium when manufacturing the MMC by liquid metal infiltration. The thickness of the reaction zone was no more than $0.2\mu\text{m}$ when a melt temperature of 700°C. was used, but when the higher temperature ($\sim 900^\circ\text{C}$.) was employed the reaction was such that it often accounted for more than one half of the fibre volume. Magnesium was found to have penetrated the outermost layer of the fibre where it formed magnesium oxide. A corresponding decrease in the amount of silicon was recorded, the freed silicon diffusing into the metal matrix to form magnesium silicide, Mg_2Si . In the composite manufactured at the higher temperature, there was evidence that carbon also had been released from the fibre and it then combined with some of the freed silicon to form SiC particles close to the fibre interface.

Previous studies (3) have indicated that Nicalon fibre consists of free carbon and silicon oxycarbide as well as silicon carbide, but the extent to which each constituent has been involved in the reaction with magnesium is uncertain from the present results. There is strong evidence, however, that the silicon carbide phase in the fibre has not been appreciably affected, particularly since SiC particles were formed elsewhere as a stable phase in the matrix during processing. This supports the idea that the silicon which was released from the fibre was originally associated with the silicon oxycarbide phase. Further, it is contended that the magnesium was attracted by the oxygen in this constituent, where it replaced silicon to form an oxide. It might also be argued that such breakdown of oxycarbide provided the carbon which entered the matrix, although this does not rule out the possibility that some of the free carbon present in the original fibre has been involved in the reaction. What is, however, apparent is that the amounts of magnesium and oxygen measured in the reacted fibre zone do not equate exactly with MgO, which suggests that some Mg-containing oxycarbide may have also formed. With regard to the presence of an magnesium/aluminium spinel in the 900°C. composite, this is a consequence of aluminium (~3 %) being present in the matrix alloy and it is likely that the phase relates to conditions in the melt rather than breakdown of the oxycarbide. Finally, it may be worth mentioning that the surface layer of silica (~ 20nm thick) which was revealed in earlier work (3) to be present on the fibre, may have acted in some way to initiate the chemical reaction. It is hoped that some questions concerning the nature of the chemical state of constituent atoms may be answered when studies are completed of the fine structure of x-ray emission lines from the fibre.

As far as the mechanical properties of the MMC were concerned, a consequence of the fibre/matrix reaction was the development of voids and cavitation at the interface, particularly in the MMC manufactured at the higher temperature. Severe loss of cohesion between fibre and matrix then occurred such that the MMC was unable to sustain much load and broke in a brittle fashion when stressed. Thus the crack path was little deflected by those fibres which had been heavily reacted and only slightly by fibres which were partially reacted (Fig 7). The matrix second phases, especially the large magnesium silicide particles, were also found to be detrimental to the mechanical properties of the composite due to the fact that they fractured in an extremely brittle manner with frequent cleavage along the edge of the phase. Similar embrittlement effects caused by Mg₂Si particles have been reported (4) in aluminium-zinc-magnesium alloys reinforced with Sicabo fibres.

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(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. (a) Nicalon reinforced magnesium, optical micrograph. (b) Backscattered electron image (SEM) showing some reaction between fibre and matrix.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 2. As Fig. 1. (a) Interface between Nicalon fibre and matrix showing reaction zone, TEM. (b) SAD taken from fibre core, X, showing β -SiC. (c) SAD from reaction zone, Y, showing β -SiC and MgO.

Fig. 3. As Fig. 2. (a) EDS trace from fibre core X.
 (b) EDS trace from reaction zone Y.

Fig. 4. As Fig. 2. (a) Matrix second phase, S, TEM. (b) EDS trace from S. (c) SAD from S showing Mg_2Si structure. (d) Analysis of SAD pattern.

Fig. 5. Nicalon reinforced AZ31 alloy, optical micrograph.

Fig. 6. As Fig. 5. Backscattered electron image showing compositional differences especially in the fibres.

Fig. 7. Nicalon reinforced AZ31 tested in four-point bend; fracture surface showing fibres and matrix second phases, SEM.